

1 **A neurotransmission system enriched in the primary tumor of humans with breast cancer provides**
2 **evidence for neurochemical support of the tumor life cycle through a paracrine mechanism**
3 **connecting the primary tumor, lymph node and the CNS.**

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8 Neurotrophic factors, axon guidance molecules and components of the neurotransmission system recently
9 defined were enriched in the primary tumors of humans with lymph node positive breast cancer as
10 compared to those without lymph node metastasis.
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